

A MODERN INTERPRETATION OF PUBLICISTIC STYLE AND MEANS OF EXPRESSING ITS ESSENCE

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Abstract. *The article analyzes the modern interpretation of the publicistic style, its methodological and communicative features, and its place in the socio-information space. The author sheds light on new aspects of the publicistic style associated with modern journalism, information technologies, and mass communication processes, and explains its impact on the consciousness and culture of society from a scientific point of view. The article also analyzes the means of influence of the publicistic style, the role of the author's personality, and the emotional and logical capabilities of language in their interrelation.*

Keywords: *journalism, publicism, image creation, publicistic creativity, publicistic material, information space, modern media, language and style.*

Introduction. One of the areas that provides mass influence through words, speech and text, which are the main means of exchanging information and ideas in any society, is publicism. Publicism is not only an important means of describing events and incidents, but also of forming public consciousness, strengthening civic positions, and analyzing and evaluating socio-political processes in society. In the modern media environment, the publicistic style is actively manifested not only on the pages of traditional newspapers and magazines, but also through Internet publications, blogs, and electronic media. Therefore, studying its methodological features, means of influence and expressive mechanisms from the point of view of the requirements of the new era is of great importance.

In studying the modern interpretation of the publicistic style, socio-political changes in society, the active power of language, the author's personality and the system of communication with the audience are analyzed in an interconnected manner. In a publicistic text, the harmony of facts, analysis, emotions, and imagery demonstrates the author's professional skills. In addition, new technologies, media tools, and global communication systems in this field are contributing to the enrichment of the publicistic style in terms of content and form. From this point of view, this article will provide a scientific overview of the modern interpretation of the publicistic style, the means of expressing its essence, its role in the life of society, and its social, spiritual, and moral tasks.

The main part. "Publicism is texts with socio-political and scientific content, texts about the life of the state and society. It is close to journalism, literature, and other forms of art. Publicism reflects important political, economic, philosophical, and moral issues of society, and its subject is real social life—past, present, and future. A publicist is a creative individual who openly and actively influences the processes of time and society." Because publicism is not a mission, it does not consider its point of view to be the only correct one and does not try to impose it. It has its own approach and direction to the situation, to the essence. It is important to convey this to the reader, to encourage him to think. The publicist must be able to think not with his inner "I", but at the

level of the collective interest - the general "I". He must accept the outside world, the fate of strangers as his own. Publicism is not just a literary text full of emotions, passions, it collects evidence, studies special literature, conducts interviews - all this is put into a logical system and analyzed, and through this a connection is established between the journalist and the reader.

“Publicism can be compared to a refined woman. A woman without refinement does not resemble a real woman. Publicism without imagery cannot be true publicism” - says Anatoly Kozlov. Moreover, the combination of evidence, emotion, and imagery through ideal views based on reality demonstrates the journalistic skill. Publicism is not about standing on the shore and observing the process in a river, but about flowing with the current, sometimes swimming against it. At the center of publicism are always global problems, and the author analyzes them. According to scientist Anatoly Kozlov, publicistic creativity can be studied in four ways. They are as follows:

1. Publicism as a means of influence: any person who wants to promote his idea chooses publicism as a way of influence. Orators such as Demosthenes, Aeschylus, and Lysias influenced the people in this way. Even today, publicism helps in spreading a certain idea in political situations, election campaigns, and among organized people.

2. “Publicism as a means of studying society: society does not live only in everyday life, economic, political, cultural, and social spheres have their place in it, and this place sometimes requires someone to deeply analyze and explain to the public the opportunities, privileges, problems, and shortcomings”; publicists study the life of society in order to improve some aspects in order to achieve an active life.

3. Publicism as a field of study of man: in the study of an individual, genres of literary journalism are used, that is, through the genres of essay, literary portrait, the character of a particular person is revealed, heroic or ordinary human traits are embodied before the reader's eyes.

4. Publicism as a means of expressing one's own opinion, self-study, and informing the outside world about it: publicism also serves as a means of self-study by the author. In this, memories, descriptions and analysis of everyday events play a key role. The work of the Russian writer Leo Tolstoy "Confession" can be an example of such self-study and analysis journalism.

Publicism assesses the state of society, shows its shortcomings, seeks its causes and consequences, deeply analyzes them, and serves to contribute to the positive change of the process. The term “publicism” is interpreted both in a broad and narrow sense. “In some cases, this can be journalism, and sometimes it can be just its individual forms or authorial material that reflects the socio-political position of the citizen”.

In this regard, it is necessary to clearly distinguish between the concepts of publicism and journalism. "If the first is primarily a creative activity that reflects life events in their natural development and reflects socio-political changes and processes, then journalism is a social institution, a specific type of activity of people engaged in a specific profession. It can be said that publicism is a specific type of literature, along with scientific and artistic literature. We can say that it has long been formed as a special form of reflection of reality, propaganda and the formation of public consciousness by the creator". Theoretical approaches in modern scientific research on the study of publicism are diverse, which indicates that researchers cannot find a common basis for determining the subject and essence of publicism. In most theoretical studies, publicism is studied as an activity that describes reality. This activity recognizes social and political life. Theorists approach it based on the etymology of the term publicism: “publicus” (lat.) - “public”. V.I. Zdorovega considers “all public speeches on current socio-political topics” to be publicism.

Other researchers, including Z.V.Senuk, describe publicism as a method of social activity carried out using creative methods and mass media: “The creation of publicistic images by a subject through various signs in order to promote one or another idea in society.” This approach to publicism can also be seen in the works of T. Kazokbaev and M. Khudoikulov: “Publicism in its true sense is a spoken word, a written text, a work of a certain form, which becomes an ideological, political and spiritual force only when it is transferred to the pages of journalism, is published on radio, television, and the Internet”. Publicism participates in the formation of political culture, has a strong influence on the processes of social regulation and political socialization of society. Publicism, which is active in political and ideological processes, also forms social ideas and demonstrates them in the process of public communication.

Publicism can be studied according to its social functions. This is a type of creative process aimed at continuous influence on public opinion: methods and means of persuasive impact of publicist word, various valid arguments, etc. are important in this. In this respect, publicism is described as one of the forms of public propaganda, as a tool of social management and organization. In the theoretical concept of E.P. Prokhorov, the concept of "publicism" is determined by a specific category of addressee. In his opinion, publicism is closely related to its counteragents - public opinion: "...the creative specificity of publicism directly depends on its social function - direct participation in public opinion". The author of a publicistic work acts as a public representative; journalistic text expresses generally accepted opinions.

According to S.Umirov: "After many years of debate among experts, the definition of the famous researcher Evgeny Prokhorov in the 1970s, which means "publicism is a field that captures social issues and problems in writing, shapes public opinion, influences the public consciousness, and works with logical discussion and figurative thinking based on evidence and examples," was found acceptable and taken as the basis". Yu.Surovtseva studies publicism as a unique method of description. According to her, “the subject of publicism is extremely diverse and its important feature is its publicness”.

M.S.Cherepakhov proposes a comprehensive approach to the study of publicism. “In his concept, publicism is one of the three independent types of knowledge of truth, called “types of literature,” standing on a par with scientific (scientific-popular) and fiction. The specificity of its subject, content and tasks, methods of knowledge and form allows the researcher to distinguish journalism as a separate type of literature. To determine the subject of publicism, the scientist determines its difference from knowledge about life - science and art. The task of publicism is to search for the truth. Fiction serves the purpose of aesthetic knowledge of life and man. The leading feature of publicism is “...a political understanding of reality, carried out for the purposes of propaganda and propaganda, and as a result of which it affects the political consciousness of the masses”.

When considering the essence of journalistic creativity, one can observe contradictory opinions and different interpretations of this concept in specialized literature. Because many people consider journalism to be the same as publicistic creativity. Some scholars pay attention to such definitions as: “publicism as a creative process”, “publicism in the world of creative forms”. Based on this approach, journalism is viewed primarily as the organization of editorial and journalistic work, and the creative process itself is also closely related to publicism. It is recognized as a literary genre that is intermediate between artistic and scientific creativity, but related to them.

Some researchers consider publicism as a socio-political creative activity. According to the well-known scientist Saidi Umirov: “The reader is looking for a new, deep thought, a high, true

idea in publicism. A person who writes well does not write well, but a person who thinks well writes well. I see the skill of a journalist, first of all, in the exploration, understanding, and presentation of new evidence, new facts, new problems, new events. There is no problem-free journalism at all. And we often end up making declarations instead of convincing. Publicism is a struggle, establishing new things in our lives, eliminating the vices that hinder our progress”.

There is no consensus on this issue among practitioners. Often, the terms "journalistic material" and "publicistic material" are used interchangeably. Indeed, in many cases, the concepts of “journalism” and “publicity” are used interchangeably. That is, publicism is, first of all, an activity that collects, processes, and periodically disseminates relevant information through the press, radio, and television; secondly, it is understood as a set of creative materials of periodicals of newspapers and magazines. V.M.Gorokhov defines publicism as the highest type of journalism. When compared with information journalism, publicism is distinguished by the author's attitude, principles, conceptualism, scope of conclusions and generalizations, and the breadth of interpretation of problems of social life. Publicism is a powerful tool that can turn even mediocre news into a serious article. The level of a journalist is reflected in how a publicist's article turns out. Publicism manifests itself in various forms in the creative work of a speaker, critic, writer, and journalist. Truth is the goal of a publicist's vision. A publicist does not deal with a single fact, but studies it from all sides.

The development of journalism in our country is directly related to the current state of publicism. The formation of publicism in our country took place under the influence of various complex processes in the development of society: socio-political changes, technological improvements and the evolution of communication methods, economic and political reforms that have strengthened the ties of international culture. As bright representatives of modern publicism in our country, it is necessary to recognize Boybuta Dustkaraev, Akhmad Muhammad Tursun, Amir Fayzulla, Saidi Umirov, Khurshid Dustmuhammad, Akhmadjon Meliboev, Safar Oston, Karim Bahriev, Olimjon Usarov, Halim Saidov, Salim Doniyarov, Farmon Toshev, Muhammadjon Obidov and others.

Conclusion. Publicism is not just a means of conveying information, but also a creative form of understanding, analyzing and contributing to the development of society. Its main essence is to influence public opinion, raise social issues and actively participate in their solution. The modern interpretation of the publicistic style is that it relies not only on artistic imagery and emotion, but also on logical analysis, evidence and social responsibility. A modern publicist is not limited to conveying information - he activates the consciousness of society, encourages the reader to think, analyze and form an active civic position. The effectiveness of publicism is determined, first of all, by the author's worldview, language skills, style of speech and social position. In this regard, modern publicism reflects the connection between information technologies, journalism and literature, and plays an important role as a spiritual and cultural mirror of the development of society. Thus, the essence of the publicistic style is to illuminate the current issues of life through humanitarian, emotional and logical analysis, to express thoughts and feelings harmoniously, to educate public consciousness and to stimulate social activity.

REFERENCES

1. Ирназаров Қ.Т. ва бошқалар. Ҳозирги замон журналистикаси. – Т.: Алоқачи, 2008. - Б.15.

2. Горохов В.М. Закономерности публицистического творчества: (Пресса и публицистика). – М.: Мысль, 1975. - С. 23.
3. Здровега В.И. Слово тоже есть дело. М.: 1979. – С.14.
4. Қозокбоев Т., Худойкулов М. Журналистикага кириш. – Т.: Иқтисод-Молия, 2018. – Б.169.
5. Корконосенко С.Г. Социальное управление и печать: Учеб. пособие. Л.: Изд-во Ленингр. гос. ун-та, 1989. - С. 9.
6. Прохоров Е.П. Искусство публицистики: Размышления и разборы. –М.: Сов. писатель, 1984. - С. 27.
7. Сенук З.В. Публицистика как фактор развития политической культуры: Автореф. дис. ... канд. филос. наук. Екатеринбург, 1993. 10 с.
8. Суровцев Ю. О публицистике и публицистичности // Знамя. 1986. №4. - С. 217.
9. Умиров С. Сехрли ва меҳрли сўз. –Т.: Бодомзор инвест. 2017. –Б.196.
10. Умиров С. Дорилфунунлар тақдиримда. –Т.: Шарқ, 2008. - Б. 113.
11. Черепухов М.С. Проблемы теории публицистики. 2-е изд., перераб.и доп. – М.: Мысль, 1973. – С.267.